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External program evaluations and institutional reviews

A comparative overview and case study

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INTRODUCTION

Higher education is constantly changing to adapt to internal and external needs, pressures and opportunities. This in turn has prompted organisations worldwide to develop mechanisms for quality assurance and accreditation so as to stay in control of the quality of higher education [1,2,3].

Even if there is not one quality assurance (QA) model that applies universally, many do have features in common [4]. Yet these frameworks are by no means carved in stone. Revisions are common in response to new insights [5], critique [6] and changes in contexts [1,3,7]. Literature also shows that the way QA is shaped in turn influences policy and processes [2,8].

This paper provides insight in one such revision. In recent years, external QA in the Dutch-speaking part of Belgium has made the transition from a model based on program evaluations to institutional reviews. The paper starts with an introduction to literature on external QA. Subsequently, a comparative overview of two frameworks and a case study in an engineering technology faculty are presented.

1 EXTERNAL QUALITY ASSURANCE IN INTERNATIONAL PERSPECTIVE

1.1 Definition and purpose

Literature reports several definitions for quality and quality assurance, alternatingly inspired by idealistic, academic, pedagogic, managerial and consumerist values [2,6,7,8]. Indeed, it will not be surprising that expectations towards quality assurance

are equally diverse as the stakeholders involved in higher education. In its essence, quality assurance is a means to provide reliable information to stakeholders so as to allow optimal decision-making [5].

QA's twin purposes reveal its dual nature: it is aimed at both accountability and quality enhancement – though not always in equal measure. Continuous enhancement was a consideration from the start. It was dwarfed immediately, though, by attesting efficient use of resources [1,4]. Current affairs played a key role in this. In most countries, QA was introduced as a way to deal with growing concerns about the quality of higher education. Expanding student numbers, rising awareness on dropout rates, and demands for accountability about public spending were their cause. Ensuring that students' qualifications and expectations remained at the forefront of institutional missions, in spite of context changes, had to empower higher education institutions (HEIs) to defend their institutional autonomy. This was achieved by guaranteeing compliance with (minimum) standards, by providing information, and by building trust. Up to this day, successful QA is often a requirement to further operate a program or an institution. In some countries it also affects public funding, whereas in others the HEI or programs simply receive recommendations for improvement [3,7,9].

1.2 Emergence and trends

The U.S. were the trendsetter with regard to external QA. Nowadays similar models have been adopted elsewhere as well, at different speeds. Cross-Atlantic and intra-European influences are still apparent [7]. Frameworks such as the European Standards and Guidelines provide guiding principles and standards to improve the quality of QA models [3]. Several models and combinations thereof are commonplace: program evaluations, institutional reviews, students' ratings of education, performance contracts, and total quality management systems [2,7]. Responsibility for these processes is awarded to either one or more private organisations or to statutory agencies [5,9]. Historical structures, practicalities and context changes affect the way QA is implemented. Even so, similarities remain because of normative influences, coercive legislation and mimetic tendencies to imitate good practices [7].

Current trends are a growing consideration for self-improvement, taking into account institutional diversity, and stronger stakeholder involvement. Many agencies are also opting for lighter, formative procedures in favour of HEIs' own responsibility for QA [3,4]. These are not universal tendencies, though. Radical reforms in opposite directions have also been observed, such as The Netherlands' transition from soft self-regulation to stringent performance contracts [6].

1.3 Impact

The impact of QA can be substantial. The way a QA model is shaped is said to influence allocation of resources, academic autonomy, legitimacy, internal power balance, decision-making processes, political power and consumer influence [2]. It can be a strong driver for internal QA and stakeholder involvement [8]. Notwithstanding, it can also cause bureaucracy and alienate academic staff [1]. Whether the impact is mostly desirable or detrimental depends upon how the system is implemented. Its effects can also be ambiguous as is shown in literature. Minimum standards may be met yet innovation inhibited. Strengths endorsed yet weaknesses concealed [1,3,5]. To be able to concede institutional autonomy, it seems one needs at least sufficient internalisation of standards and managerial capacity [8]. Careful deliberation and guidance on the best way to implement QA are therefore imperative.

2 PROGRAM EVALUATION VS. INSTITUTIONAL REVIEW

The remainder of this paper will focus on two models for external QA in higher education: program evaluations and institutional reviews.

In Flanders, program evaluations were introduced in 2005. In 2015, exactly one decade later, a new QA system was decreed. This offered HEIs the possibility to choose between either program evaluations or institutional reviews with selected in-depth review trails. Every single HEI has opted for the transition to institutional reviews with review trails. A periodic positive advice by a commission of external experts, appointed by a governmental organization, was and still is a necessary condition for initial or further accreditation [10,11].

2.1 Method

The comparative overview is based on content analysis of the frameworks for program evaluations and institutional reviews published by the coordinating Accreditation Organisation of the Netherlands and Flanders [10] and by the delegated Flemish organisation VLUHR QA [11]. The protocols date from early 2015, the same year as the case study discussed in section 3.

2.2 Comparative overview

Program evaluations and institutional reviews are similar in some ways but also differ in many others, as is evident from the summary in *Table 1* below.

Some similarities are easy to spot. Both frameworks include the typical four elements in early U.S. models and current European models as described in literature [3,7]. These are a self-assessment report by the HEI, a site visit by a commission of external peers, compilation of a review report by the commission, and follow-up by the HEI and external authority.

The most fundamental differences are the approach and topics. Again in line with literature [3], program evaluations apply content-related indicators whereas institutional reviews adopt a systemic quality management perspective. The focus in other words shifts from inputs and outputs to processes.

Both models use ordinal scales to rate criteria as well as to give an overall rating. The scales vary in the number of possible outcomes and semantic meaning. Literature identifies two main types of scales: excellence-oriented and compliance-oriented scales [3]. Program evaluations use excellence-oriented scales to rate each topic: standards can be exceeded. In the institutional review's compliance-oriented scale on the other hand, the best value corresponds to adequacy. Both use a compliance-oriented scale for the overall rating.

Both types of assessments focus increasingly on accountability as of 2005, in addition to quality improvement, states VLUHR QA explicitly [11].

Table 1. Comparative overview of external QA models in Flanders, 2015-2016.

	Program evaluation	Institutional review
Aim	Quality enhancement as well as accountability	
Approach	Traditional, Q&A: "Does the institution have a good model?"	Appreciative, dialogue: "Does the institution's model work?"
Reference	Compliance	Own model/story

Assessment framework topics	1) Intended exit level 2) Teaching-learning environment 3) Achieved level	1) Vision and policy 2) Policy implementation 3) Evaluation and monitoring 4) Enhancement policy
Expected input by HEI	Self-evaluation report, list of required appendices.	Critical reflection report, limited appendices.
Composition of commission	4 independent members, incl. 1 student. Expertise in: subject/discipline, professional field, education, international HE, auditing	5 independent members, incl. 1 student. Expertise in: policy, education, international HE, auditing
Panel groups during site visit	Management, lecturers, students, alumni, professional field	Board, management, QA experts, lecturers, students, professional field
Duration of site visit	1 visit, 1-2 days	2 visits, in total 2-5 days
Topic assessment scale	Excellent / good / sufficient / insufficient	Meets standard / partially meets standard / does not meet standard
Final assessment scale	Satisfactory / satisfactory with limited validity / unsatisfactory	Positive / conditionally positive / negative
Timing	Once every 8 years	Once every 6 years

3 CASE STUDY

The Faculty of Engineering Technology of KU Leuven (Catholic University of Leuven) has been involved in both models in recent years. One of its bachelor programs was the subject of the last round of external program evaluations in 2015. Being a newly established multi-campus faculty subsequently made it an indispensable review trail for the university's first institutional review in 2016, to assess whether the HEI's policy and QA system also functioned in a highly complex context.

3.1 Method

Individual in-depth interviews with semi-structured questions were used to explore internal stakeholders' experiences. The interviews were conducted in April-May 2018 with audio recording and transcription afterwards. Subjects were selected based on their involvement in the program evaluation of 2015 as well as in the trail in the more recent institutional review in 2016. Twelve subjects were contacted and all participated in the study: the faculty's vice-dean; several program directors, vice-campus chairs and student representatives; and two educational developers. Some interviewees had also been involved in QA cycles prior to 2015. Each subsection below is introduced by one or more quotes illustrating the interviewees' main thoughts on the topic.

3.2 Topic 1: Preparations and involvement

"You are forced to reflect on why the curriculum is as it is, its strengths and weaknesses. The day-to-day flow does not always provide the same awareness." (Program director/vice-campus chair)

The preparations for a program evaluation were looked back on as a very intensive process. The self-evaluation report in particular evoked many memories. First thoughts centred around it being an extremely time-consuming activity, fear to write something that could be misinterpreted, and respect for those who spent evenings and

weekends working on documents on top of their regular workload. The community and support behind the efforts might not always be equally visible to outsiders. The student representatives recalled it as being initially overwhelming because they were less familiar with the procedure and topics discussed. At the same time they felt they could be of added value by providing a fresh pair of eyes. Moreover, many interviewees immediately countered their initial reactions by saying that all in all, looking back, it had been a strong learning experience, as testified by the quote above.

The preparations relating to practical matters and required appendices on the other hand were not considered worth the effort. If the same program was evaluated multiple times the perceived usefulness also declined.

The preparations for the institutional review were a completely different story. The appreciative approach made it a fundamentally different exercise as the HEI had to look in a critical manner at the own model instead of anticipating which critique was to be expected from external peers. The interviewees also appreciated that they no longer had to be the key players in each step of the preparations. Several regretted though that the feeling of involvement and the learning effect were equally lost.

3.3 Topic 2: The site visit

“A program evaluation feels like an exam, whereas an institutional review is more like a performance appraisal.” (Vice-campus chair)

The commission's visit was often exciting, feeling very much like an examination (as illustrated above). The limited time only left room for selected topics and made it important to give a strong first impression. With program evaluations, it sometimes felt like giving a sales pitch. The commission also did not refrain from asking tough questions or digging for flaws. The institutional review felt more like a dialogue.

The interviewees overall had a positive feeling with regard to the group interviews by the commissions. It could not have been easy for the commission members, reflected many. Yet the commission members were perceived as well trained and performing with neutrality and objectivity. Surely, sometimes one commission member dominated and many had pet subjects. Almost every interviewee mentioned this. This did not bother them as long as it did not influence the conversations all too much. The student representatives appreciated there also being a student commission member.

Three interviewees remarked that the group aspect might be a methodological weakness: the conversation was sometimes highly determined by those who spoke first or by the presence or absence of one participant with a specific perspective.

3.4 Topic 3: Reliability and outcomes

“The info provided in external evaluations is Facebook-honest or Instagram-honest. What you show is yours, with the only difference that everybody is happy.” (Program director/vice-campus chair)

“The commission most of all determines whether you have been honest in your self-evaluation. The steps taken in-house, i.e. identifying points of improvement and taking action, are more significant than the evaluation itself.” (Program director)

The overall reliability was perceived as adequate (e.g. quotes). The interviewees expect a well-trained program evaluation commission to see through cover-ups during

the site visit. Stakeholders will obviously stress strengths rather than weaknesses as their reputation is at stake. Nevertheless, it was perceived an ethical obligation to be honest and safer than to risk being exposed. Subjects did wonder if institutional reviews will prove equally reliable. Opinions were divided on whether the appreciative approach and dialogue will generate mostly distraction from flaws or sincerity.

In program evaluations, the interviewees do consider it necessary for the commission to visit every campus. The wide topic array made the evaluation feel thorough and reliable. The interviewees remarked that the institutional review did not include these two features, but perhaps did not need these either because of the shift in perspective.

The conclusions published in the program evaluation reports were rarely a surprise. Often these mostly repeated what was described in the self-evaluation report. Some interviewees were disappointed that a commission had not noticed or affirmed certain strengths regarded as a major step forward by those involved. The institutional review report on the other hand had not really made an impression as it only discussed the institution's model, not the trails in particular. Factual errors in both reports were no exception. Subjects did appreciate the commission mentioning a strength for each individual campus. Overall, though, because of to the reasons listed above, subjects felt rather dissatisfied with or indifferent about the reports.

3.5 Topic 4: Impact on other processes

“Teambuilding! Fighting for a common goal against a common enemy is very beneficial to grow as a team.” (Vice-dean)

Many interviewees referred to the emotional, psychological impact of the program evaluation in the newly established faculty. Working on the self-evaluation report not only generated awareness on each campus's strengths and opportunities, it also made them consider each other more as colleagues (e.g. quote). Getting a positive evaluation in addition provided very welcome confirmation on the choices made so far.

External evaluations also seem to provide strong leverage to initiate actions and make decisions. At least in the short term. Extensive reforms were more often postponed until after the site visit so as not to create inconsistencies between the self-evaluation report and the situation at the time of the commission's visit.

The institutional review boosted the implementation of a stronger internal QA system. Points of improvement suggested by previous program evaluation commission were often given low priority until right before a new evaluation was due. The institutional review made sure a more continuous QA approach was adopted.

3.6 Topic 5: General reflections and recommendations

“Our internal QA system has taken over most of the strengths of the former program evaluations.” (Student representative)

Asked about their opinion on the switch from program evaluations to institutional reviews, most interviewees argued in favour of the new model. The quote above mentions only one of the reasons for this. The appreciative approach and clustered level in particular furthermore made for a more positive experience and more balanced workload. They also felt the HEI was ready to take its responsibility.

The most adequate level for an external review might be situated somewhere between the program and institutional level, nevertheless, some said. Many cautioned we

should also retain interaction between lecturers and external peers at the program level, and should make programs face the facts in case of real issues. Including peers from the professional field and from other higher education programs in the internal QA system could suffice. Others suggested complementing regular institutional reviews with occasional program evaluations.

4 DISCUSSION

4.1 Conclusions

By discussing experiences with two external QA models, this paper aimed to generate awareness of the potential value of programs evaluations and institutional reviews to support other countries who wish to implement one or both of these. The QA models in Flanders indeed show many similarities to frameworks in other countries, both in their aim and in the way they are implemented [3,7]. The comparative overview and case study presented in this paper furthermore reflected international trends, such as growing attention to institutional diversity and offering responsibility for QA [3,4].

Overall, program evaluations and institutional reviews both have their merits. The case study provided examples on their potential impact. The traditional approach in program evaluations seemed to cause stakeholders to perceive it as a deficit-focused system, focussing on quality as value for money or perfection. The institutional review's appreciative approach on the other hand made it a framework where quality was contemplated as fitness for purpose or transforming. These different perspectives on quality as also mentioned in literature [6,7] made for completely different experiences, as was apparent from the interviews. The strengths of one model seemed to be the weaknesses of the other, and vice versa. Program evaluations commonly provided stronger recognition of the program's own strengths and weaknesses yet were a very intensive process. Institutional reviews then again allowed for more resources to be invested in the internal QA system though may become a remote issue for most stakeholders except management. The main challenge remains to create a model that manages to combine involvement with a feasible workload. A complementary internal QA system should subsequently be able to amplify its strengths and counterbalance its weaknesses to achieve the best possible results.

4.2 Strengths, limitations and directions for future research

An earlier paper already described some challenges posed by program evaluations [9]. This paper discusses the same QA model from a different perspective and compares it to the new institutional review model introduced in the meantime.

A strength of the current paper is its multimethod design. Content analysis and literature review provide insight in QA models. A case study complements this by presenting how these models and their impact are experienced in practice.

The time elapsed between the external evaluations and the interviews offered the subjects the necessary distance to look back in a rational manner. On the other hand, obviously, these remain self-reported retrospections stemming from a very specific context, i.e. a newly established faculty. Future research might investigate whether these models provide similar experiences in other contexts or attempt to measure the impact of different QA models by means of mixed methods.

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